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Pd stabilized on nanocomposite of halloysite and β -cyclodextrin derived carbon: An efficient catalyst for hydrogenation of nitroarene

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Abstract

Carbon nanospheres, CCDs, were fabricated using β -cyclodextrin as carbon precursor. The as prepared CCD was then hybridized with halloysite nanotubes (Hal) through hydrothermal treatment to furnish a nanocomposite, Hal-CCD that was subsequently applied as support to stabilize Pd nanoparticles. Investigation of the catalytic activity of palladated nanocomposite, Pd@Hal-CCD, for the hydrogenation reaction of nitrobenzenes confirmed that Pd@Hal-CCD could efficiently promote the hydrogenation reaction under mild reaction condition. Moreover, the catalyst was recyclable and showed slight Pd leaching upon reusing. The comparison of the catalytic activity of Pd@Hal-CCD with that of Pd@Hal and Pd@CCD indicated the superior catalytic activity of the former. The observed high catalytic activity of the catalyst was attributed to its higher Pd loading and water disperse ability. Additionally, the results confirmed that the ratio of Hal:CCD could affect the catalytic activity and the best result was obtained by using Hal:CCD ratio of 1:2.

Keywords: β -Cyclodextrin, Nanospheres, Halloysite, Heterogeneous, catalysts, Hydrogenation